

Building the future you were promised

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Keywords:

1. Introduction

In order to ride the exponential curve that Machine Intelligence is generating, business must have a strategy that integrates it into whatever facet they can in order to survive and be relevant. We will discuss the why and how in order to inform your MOM.

2. Aim

Machine Intelligence is now and forever. If you aren't actively approaching it as your focus on technology implementation you're already behind. Also, endpoint experiences should drive the application of machine intelligence. Our hope is that the audience will take a different look at how all of the technology they are developing can benefit from spending more time understanding how the technology will be best used to augment the human experience.

3. Material and methods

CUBE

4. Results

More and more companies are starting to align and understand that MI is a thing they need but have no clue how to do it.

5. Conclusions

If your company doesn't have a Machine Intelligence strategy - your company will die.

6. Keywords

Innovation, Machine Intelligence, Inspiration, Excellent, Maximum Bodacity

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